

GENDER ROLES IN GENDER-MARKED PHRASEOLOGISMS-A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND GEORGIAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

Gender roles are an important social construct that is manifested through language in different cultures. Language is not only a tool of communication, but also reflects the values of society, its established norms and stereotypes. Particular interest lies in gender-marked phraseologisms, which allow cross-cultural comparisons.

This study conducts a comparative analysis of gender-marked phraseologisms in English and Georgian in order to reveal their cultural-historical foundations, reflection of gender roles and linguistic transformations. The aim of the study is to analyze how these phraseologisms represent masculine and feminine qualities, how they have changed over time and how the modification of gender stereotypes is reflected in the language.

The research methodology includes the analysis of phraseological units, the investigation of historical-etymological parallels, and the application of gender-linguistic theories. The results show that, despite cultural differences, many gender-marked phraseology in English and Georgian share common stereotypical notions of male power, female subordination, family roles, and emotional attributes.

However, the study also revealed trends in linguistic transformations that reflect changes in the perception of gender roles in modern society. This process is especially evident in the emergence of neutral or gender-inclusive alternative expressions.

The study will make a significant contribution to gender linguistics, phraseology, and cross-cultural language studies, which will allow us to better understand how language influences the formation of gender identities.

Keywords: gender, phraseologisms, gender roles, gender marking, linguistic stereotypes.

Gender Roles in Gender-Marked Phraseologisms: A Comparative Analysis of English and Georgian Languages

Gender roles represent a significant social construct that manifests through language in cultures and societies. Language, as the primary means of communication and cultural transmission, plays a crucial role in shaping gender identities (Lakoff, 1975).

Phraseologisms, as stable elements of language, serve not only to simplify communication but also to transmit cultural heritage and ideology (Goddard and Wierzbicka, 2014). The aim of the study is to explore how language reflects existing gender stereotypes in society and how these stereotypes have evolved over time.

The study employs a comparative analysis, utilizing lexicographical sources and theories of gender linguistics (Holmes and Meyerhoff, 2003). In languages, gender marking is manifested in various ways, including through direct nominative forms and metaphorical constructions (Hellinger and Bußmann, 2001). There are numerous phraseologisms that directly reflect gender stereotypes and the gender roles shaped according to these stereotypes.

Gender-marked phraseologisms highlight the linguistic features that reflect the gender role stereotypes present in society. Both in Georgian and English, numerous phraseological units contain gender markers that have developed as a result of cultural context and historical evolution.

A woman is often associated with beauty, obedience, or emotional vulnerability. In both Georgian and English, there are numerous phraseologisms that reflect these characteristics. In both languages, the patriarchal structure is evident, where a woman is expected to serve the family. In both languages, a woman is either idealized or demonized, and she is predominantly portrayed as a weak and defenseless being in need of protection.

In both Georgian and English, a man is often associated with strength, bravery, intelligence, and leadership. Phraseologisms referring to men indicate their responsibility within the family and society. A man should be modest, and his word should hold value, while a woman is considered eloquent in speech. In both languages, a man is either expected to be physically strong or intelligent. Both reflect a patriarchal perception that a man is the leader in the family. In Georgian, there is an emphasis on traditional gender roles, while in English, there is a normalization of male behavior. If we look at different phraseologisms in Georgian and English, we can see that some social attitudes and beliefs determine and dictate the roles and responsibilities which a man or a woman should or should not perform:

- „თმა გრძელი და ჭკუა მოკლე“ - „long hair little brain”, “women have long hair and short brains”
- “ქალი თმისა, მწვადი ცვრიანი” – „Woman’s hair is her crowning glory”

According to different examples, long hair is associated as a characteristic of a woman. Even nowadays when people have a freedom of choice, some solid viewpoints dictate the norms.

- “ქალის გაჩენაში ღმერთი არ ურევიაო” „ – „A woman’s work is never done”

This kind of phraseologisms show that women have a difficult live, with a lot of responsibilities. Even though men are associated to power, women are multitasked and overloaded with duties.

- “ქალი მუბლგახსნილი-კაცი მუბლმეკრული” – “A woman smiling-A man frowned”

- “ქალი მორცხვი ქვეყნის ფასი, კაცი მორცხვი კვერცხის ფასი – In this Georgian phraseology is said that if a man is shy, his value equals to the value of an egg, the men are not allowed to express emotions as women are.

There are interesting phraseologisms connected to women, like:

- “ქალი სხვისი ლუკმაო „ქალი სხვისი კერის ნაცარიაო “, „ქალი სხვათა სახლის ყორეაო “– „A woman builds her own house”

These examples illustrate the traditional dominance of men, particularly within Georgian culture. Historically, it was a firmly established custom for a man to marry and bring his wife to reside in his family home. Upon marriage, women would leave their parental households, signifying a symbolic and practical transfer from one family unit to another. Consequently, the husband's family was perceived as gaining a member, while the wife's family experienced a loss. This dynamic may partly explain the cultural preference for male offspring, whose birth was often met with greater celebration. Moreover, given Georgia's frequent involvement in warfare throughout history, sons were also valued as future defenders of both the family and the nation, further reinforcing the desirability of male children.

- „ქალი აშენებულ ოჯახს დააქცევს და დაქცეულს ააშენებსო“ – “Where devil can not come he will send women”
- „ქალი ეშმაკზე ერთი დღით ადრე არის გაჩენილიო“

Women are frequently portrayed as seductresses, unfaithful or emotionally volatile figures, often characterized by cruelty or inconsistency in mood and behavior. Such representations are evident in various proverbs, including the following examples:

- „დედაკაცი მარტსა ჰყავს, დღეში ათასგვარად იცვლება“ - “The woman is like a changeable March”
- „დედაკაცი ერთი თვალით ტირის, მეორეთი იცინის“- „Widows weep but they look for another husband”, “A rich widow weeps with one eye and signals with the other”

The role of mothers in parenting is widely regarded as crucial. Although parenting responsibilities ideally involve both parents, there remains a strong cultural emphasis on the maternal role. This emphasis likely stems from historical gender roles in which women were primarily housewives, confined to the domestic sphere, while men engaged in external labor such as hunting, working, and providing for the family. Women, in contrast, remained at home, responsible for the upbringing and education of their children. Despite the fact that in contemporary society women participate in the workforce to the same extent as men, the primary responsibility for child-rearing still disproportionately falls on mothers.

- „ქალსა დედა გაუსინჯე, ტანსაცმელსა ნაწიბური“, უდედო ქალი და უმარილო მხალიო“ “ Like mother like daughter”;

In both Georgian and English, the generic term used to refer to a human being or humanity often reflects male gender. In Georgian, the word "კაცი" (*k'atsi*), which literally means "man" or "male person," is frequently employed to refer to a person in general, regardless of gender. Similarly, in English, the term "**man**" has historically been used as a generic noun to denote all human beings. In both languages, these linguistic choices reflect a male-centered perspective, where the male term becomes the default or unmarked form in reference to humankind. This phenomenon illustrates the broader androcentric tendencies in language, where male-associated terms are normalized in contexts meant to be gender-neutral, potentially reinforcing implicit gender hierarchies.

- „მმა ძმისთვისაო-შავი დღისთვისაო“ , „წინა კაცი უკანა კაცის ხიდიაო“ , „One man’s fault is another man’s lesson”
- „კაცი გაზომე გაჭირვებაშიო“ “A friend in need is a friend indeed”
- “კაცმა შეიძლება ისწავლოს, ისწავლოს და მაინც სულელი დარჩესო”- “A man may learn and learn and yet remain a fool.”
- “კაცი რომ ორ საქმეს მოეჭიდება, ერთი უსათუოდ წაუხდებაო”- “A man cannot whistle and drink at the same time.”
- “კაცს ცოტა ეწყინება, ცოტა გაუხარდებაო”-“After rain comes sunshine (Am., Br.). Behind bad luck comes good luck (Am.).”
- “კაცს რომ ჭირი შეეყრება, ლხინზე აღარ ფიქრობსო”-“Need makes a naked man run (Am.).”
- “კაცი რომ თავის თავს უზამს, მტერი ვერ მოეკიდებაო”-“Beware of no man more than thyself (Br.).- Each man makes his own shipwreck (Am.).”

In the contemporary period, there is a noticeable trend towards the reduction of gender marking, which is linked to the growth of gender equality. Gender-marked phraseologisms are less actively used in daily communication, and there is also a replacement of terms, including those that are gender-marked. In English, more neutral phrases are emerging, such as "chairperson" instead of "chairman," while in Georgian, there are attempts to neutralize certain gender markings. Gender roles are often reflected in language, encompassing cultural expectations and stereotypes. In light of these changes, both languages (English and Georgian) are revisiting terms that traditionally reflected binary gender roles. Gender-neutral terms are becoming increasingly important in both English and Georgian.

<i>In the English language</i>	<i>In the Georgian language</i>
<i>Professions and positions:</i>	<i>Professions and positions:</i>
Actor/Actress → Actor	მსახიობი/მსახიობი ქალი → მსახიობი
Chairman → Chairperson	დირექტორი კაცი/ქალი → დირექტორი
Congressman → Legislator / Member of Congress	მეცნიერი კაცი/ქალი → მეცნიერი
Fireman → Firefighter	პოლიციელი კაცი/ქალი → პოლიციელი
Policeman → Police officer	ექიმი კაცი/ქალი → ექიმი
Stewardess → Flight attendant	ჟურნალისტი კაცი/ქალი → ჟურნალისტი
Waiter/Waitress → Server	პროფესორი კაცი/ქალი → პროფესორი
Businessman → Businessperson / Entrepreneur	მფრინავი/მფრინავი ქალი → მფრინავი
Salesman → Salesperson / Sales Representative	
Fisherman → Fisher / Angler	

<i>Family and social roles:</i>	<i>Family and Social Roles</i>
Mother/Father → Parent	ცოლი/ქმარი → მეუღლე
Brother/Sister → Sibling	ვაჟი/ქალი → შვილი
Husband/Wife → Spouse / Partner	მმა/და → დედამამიშვილი
Boyfriend/Girlfriend → Partner / Significant other	დედა/მამა → მშობელი
Son/Daughter → Child	
<i>Different Terminology:</i>	
Man-made → Artificial / Synthetic	
Manpower → Workforce / Staff	
Landlord/Landlady → Property owner	
Bachelor/Spinster → Single person	

These examples illustrate an ongoing effort to move toward gender-neutral language in Georgian, reflecting societal changes in gender equality and the diminishing of gendered roles.

The Breakdown of Gender Stereotypes in Phraseology

There are many similarities between gender-marked phraseologisms in both Georgian and English. In both languages, women are often associated with family responsibilities, beauty, and emotional sensitivity, while men are linked with leadership, strength, and intelligence. However, in English, neutral alternatives are already emerging, whereas such transformations in Georgian are progressing more slowly. The reduction of gender stereotypes and the establishment of linguistic neutrality have a significant impact on societal perception and the evolution of language. These changes contribute to the development of more inclusive communication in language.

Gender-marked phraseologisms play an important role in the construction of gender identities in both English and Georgian. However, their historical transformation reflects social changes that mirror the development of society over time.

An analysis of gender-marked phraseologisms in both English and Georgian reveals that language is not only a reflection of social reality but also an active instrument in shaping gender identities and reinforcing stereotypes. The research shows that, despite cultural and historical differences, both languages share common trends in the traditional perceptions of women's and men's roles. Specifically, phraseologisms reflect the influence of archaic notions, such as male authority, female emotionality, and the connection of women to the family.

Such a study is not only valuable from an academic perspective but also helps critically analyze the role of language in maintaining or overcoming gender inequalities.

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